

Filter for Counter Automata Construction

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ABSTRACT

We give the definition of filter which is a rational relation between the repeated sequences in non-deterministic finite automata, we also show that it can be used in constructing deterministic automata with respect to the filter condition.

Keywords: filter, counter automata, subset construction.

INTRODUCTION

Counter automata were studied before [1, 2, 3, 4], recent research shows that they can be used in a variety of problem solving [5].

FILTER

The filter itself is a boolean function in subset construction, which can be implemented “on the fly” by considering the certain stable configuration of states in non-deterministic finite automaton within the counter.

CONCLUSION

We have shown the new model of computation within the counter automata.

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